

ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN CENTRAL PERIPHERAL COCHLEOVESTIBULAR VERTEBROBASILAR INSUFFICIENCY

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Relevance of the Problem

In recent years, significant progress has been made in identifying the main causes of stroke. Still, the issue of early diagnosis of cerebrovascular disorders and the treatment of ischemic stroke remains highly relevant. A major achievement in angioneurology has been the development of a modern concept of the heterogeneity of ischemic stroke. Concerning vertebrobasilar pathology, this concept has been expanded to include the pathogenic significance of deformations and anomalies of the vertebral arteries in the development of ischemic cerebrovascular disorders.

The development of ischemic cerebral circulation disorders, taking into account their heterogeneity, is determined not only by structural changes in the vascular system but also significantly influenced by hemorheological shifts and dysfunctions in the hemostasis and fibrinolysis systems. Cerebrovascular pathology (CVP) has consistently ranked among the leading problems in medicine for many years due to its severe medical, economic, and social consequences, and the constant increase in the number of patients.

From the standpoint of modern science, it is now believed that more than half of all cases of cerebral circulation disorders are caused by pathologies of the extracranial sections of the major arteries of the head. Moreover, no less than 25% of all cases of circulatory disorders in the vertebrobasilar vascular system are directly caused by lesions of the vertebral arteries. In such cases, biomechanical dysfunctions of the cervical spine and the influence of altered spinal structures are considered

either in isolation, as the main mechanism in extravascular lesions of the vertebral arteries, or as aggravating factors in the presence of cerebral artery atherosclerosis.

This understanding stems from a re-evaluation of the previously dominant unitary concept of degenerative-dystrophic spinal disorders. However, the lack of a clear understanding of the complex mechanisms behind vertebrobasilar insufficiency often leads to inappropriate therapy. In contrast, a comprehensive and systematic approach to evaluating different variants of circulation disorders in the vertebrobasilar vascular system is clinically justified and pathogenetically sound, given that the pathological process occurs in the same anatomical structures.

Therefore, further investigation is necessary into the relationship between biomechanical disorders of the cervical spine and pathological changes in the vertebral arteries. This calls for a refined ultrasound assessment of circulatory insufficiency in the vertebrobasilar system in patients with dystrophic cervical spine lesions.

Study Objective

To optimize diagnostic methods, therapeutic correction principles, and preventive strategies for vertebrobasilar insufficiency and improve the quality of life in patients at various stages of the disease.

Study Tasks

1. Clarify the clinical features of central vertebrobasilar insufficiency and compare clinical data with ultrasound findings of extra- and intracranial cerebral arteries in atherosclerotic and spondylogenic vertebral artery lesions.
2. Identify the correlation between MRI characteristics of degenerative-dystrophic changes in the cervical spine, ultrasound results of cerebral arteries, MR angiographic features of the intracranial vertebrobasilar system, and clinical symptoms in patients with atherosclerotic and spondylogenic lesions of the vertebral arteries.
3. Based on study results, develop pathogenetically justified therapeutic correction methods and improve quality of life across different disease stages.

4. Conduct a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of traditional and combined treatments for vertebrobasilar insufficiency.

Scientific Novelty of the Results

For the first time, using extensive clinical data and modern instrumental methods for assessing cerebral hemodynamics and MRI data, specific clinical features of vertebrobasilar insufficiency have been clarified.

Using Doppler ultrasonography, duplex scanning, and MRI, new features of structural and functional changes in the major arteries of the head and neck in patients with vertebrobasilar insufficiency have been identified.

For the first time, the relationship between structural changes in the cervical spine and vertebral artery changes in patients with vertebrobasilar insufficiency has been analyzed using MRI.

Original methods for therapeutic correction and prevention of vertebrobasilar insufficiency involving manual therapy have been scientifically developed and implemented in clinical practice. The high efficacy of a proposed combined treatment method, which includes manual therapy in addition to traditional treatment, has been demonstrated.

Practical Significance

It has been established that vertebrobasilar insufficiency presents a specific syndromic complex, which is crucial in practice for diagnosis and treatment selection.

Ultrasound of the major arteries of the head and neck, MRI of the cervical and upper thoracic spine, and MR angiography of the extracranial cerebral arteries did not reveal stenotic lesions of the vertebral arteries in the transverse foramina of the cervical vertebrae in patients with spondylogenic vertebrobasilar insufficiency.

These results support the recommendation of the developed and tested combined treatment approach for vertebrobasilar insufficiency, which includes medication, manual therapy, and a specialized motor regimen, for practical healthcare use.

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